

QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PRACTICES AMONG HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN REGION XII: A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 3

Pages: 230-247

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3057

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14881714

Manuscript Accepted: 01-27-2025

Quality Management System Practices among Higher Education Institutions in Region XII: A Quantitative Analysis

Jonathan P. Roque*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

A Quality Management System (QMS) provides a structured framework of processes and procedures that organizations use to ensure consistent delivery of educational services and administrative functions that meet or exceed established quality standards. This study focused on examining the QMS practices of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII, Philippines, through a quantitative research design. Data were collected via surveys administered to deans, faculty members, and students and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that both private and public HEIs demonstrated substantial and consistent implementation of QMS practices, reflecting a commendable level of adherence in most instances. Furthermore, the results indicated no significant differences in QMS practices across HEIs, regardless of institutional type or respondent groups. The study highlighted key QMS practices commonly employed by private and public HEIs, including leadership and governance support, policy development and implementation, academic support, enriched academic environments, and robust data quality management. Based on these findings, the research proposed policy recommendations to further enhance QMS practices in HEIs. These recommendations emphasize improving communication, performance monitoring and analysis, stakeholder engagement and feedback, transparency and accountability, benchmarking, competitive analysis, and fostering professional development and well-being. The study concludes that the effective implementation of QMS practices can significantly enhance educational outcomes, stakeholder satisfaction, and institutional reputation, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and accountability within the academic environment.

Keywords: *quality management system, QMS practices, higher education institutions, leadership, quantitative research design*

Introduction

The Sustainable Development Plan for 2030 emphasizes the importance of inclusive, high-quality education worldwide, aiming to achieve universal access to primary, secondary, and higher education. In the Philippines, the pursuit of quality education remains a critical challenge as the rapid growth of higher education institutions (HEIs) has intensified competition and led to varying standards of educational quality. Although the establishment of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) through the Higher Education Act of 1994 was intended to raise educational standards, many institutions continue to face challenges in implementing effective Quality Management Systems (QMS) that align with international benchmarks.

Quality education is essential not only for the success of individual students but also for national progress, as it directly influences workforce readiness and economic development. While previous studies have examined specific aspects of QMS in higher education—such as the role of leadership in promoting a culture of quality (Bryson et al., 2018) and the importance of systematic policy development (Weldeslassie, 2021)—these studies often neglect the perspectives of key stakeholders, including students, faculty, and administrators. These perspectives are crucial for developing a comprehensive understanding of QMS practices.

Additionally, existing research tends to focus on individual institutions or specific regions, leaving a gap in comparative analyses of QMS practices across diverse HEIs in the Philippines, particularly in Region XII. This study aims to address these gaps by providing a comprehensive analysis of QMS practices in selected HEIs in Region XII, identifying the distinct challenges and opportunities encountered by these institutions. Through a focused quantitative approach, this research seeks to evaluate how QMS practices are implemented and their impact on enhancing educational quality. The findings of this study are expected to inform evidence-based policy recommendations to improve QMS practices, thereby contributing to better educational outcomes and strengthened institutional reputation within the region.

Research Questions

Generally, this study explored the quality management system (QMS) practices among HEIs in Region XII. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of practice of QMS of public and private HEIs in the following dimensions as perceived by deans, faculty, and students:
 - 1.1. leadership;
 - 1.2. strategic planning;
 - 1.3. customer focus;
 - 1.4. measurement, analysis, and knowledge management;

- 1.5. workforce focus;
- 1.6. operations focus; and
- 1.7. organization performance results?
2. Is there a significant difference in the QMS practices across categories among HEIs?
3. Is there a significant difference in the QMS practices across groups of respondents among HEIs?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research design to examine the Quality Management System (QMS) practices of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII. A survey was administered using structured questionnaires to gather numerical data on various aspects of QMS practices. The survey captured the perceptions of different respondent groups, including students, faculty, and deans, providing a comprehensive quantitative overview of QMS practices in both private and public HEIs.

The primary focus was to identify significant differences in perceptions among respondent groups or types of institutions. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were used to analyze the data, ensuring an objective and systematic evaluation of the extent and consistency of QMS implementation across HEIs. This approach enabled the identification of trends, patterns, and key areas for improvement within the QMS practices of the participating institutions.

The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the development of evidence-based policy recommendations to enhance QMS practices in HEIs, ensuring improved educational quality and institutional performance in Region XII. The quantitative framework provided a robust basis for understanding the current state of QMS implementation and its impact on institutional effectiveness.

Respondents

The study's respondents were selected through a random sampling process and included faculty members with at least five years of tenure or permanent status, deans with a minimum of two years of service, QA or QMS directors, and graduating students from four identified HEIs in Region XII. Cochran's Formula (Chaokromthong & Sintao, 2021) was utilized to determine the sample size, with a 5% precision level, 95% confidence level, and an estimated proportion of 5%. The Stratified Proportional Allocation Sampling Technique was applied to ensure representation across respondent groups. Additionally, total enumeration was used for QA or QMS directors and deans due to their limited population size.

Instrument

The study aimed to assess the level of QMS practices in four HEIs in Region XII through a meticulously developed survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed based on the Malcolm Baldrige Award Application Guidelines, with additional insights adapted from Naanep (2021). To ensure the instrument's credibility and relevance, a comprehensive validation process was undertaken. The initial draft was reviewed by the research adviser, a panel of experts, and five specialists in test construction. These reviewers evaluated each item for relevance, clarity, and suitability, providing feedback that was incorporated into the final version.

Following this, the questionnaire underwent expert validation using predefined criteria. The validators' assessments confirmed the instrument's validity and suggested refinements for improvement. To further ensure reliability, a pilot test was conducted with deans, faculty members, and students from Central Mindanao University in Bukidnon. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's coefficient alpha, which yielded an excellent result of 0.98. This exceeded the benchmark of 0.70, as recommended by Wells and Wollack, indicating a highly reliable instrument.

The final survey instrument consisted of three sections and employed a five-point Likert-type scale. It was designed to gather respondents' ratings on the seven Baldrige Education Criteria for Performance Excellence as implemented in their respective HEIs. This robust development and validation process ensured that the survey instrument was dependable and well-suited for collecting accurate and relevant data in the primary research phase.

Procedure

During the data collection phase, a survey questionnaire was utilized to ensure its relevance and effectiveness in capturing the necessary data. An endorsement letter, duly approved by the adviser and program chair, was prepared to seek the authorization of CHED RO XII for the study involving four selected HEIs in Region XII. Letters were also sent to the presidents of these HEIs, explaining the intent to administer the questionnaire to the identified respondents.

After receiving the endorsement from CHED RO XII and approval from the HEI presidents, the researcher personally delivered the request letters to the respective institutions. Upon obtaining the necessary permissions, the distribution of survey questionnaires commenced. The researcher coordinated with the Human Resource Management Office and Student Services offices in each HEI to facilitate the effective administration of the questionnaires to faculty members and students, respectively. To encourage participation among student-respondents, cellphone load tokens were provided as incentives.

All collected data were handled with strict confidentiality and used solely for research purposes, adhering to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Data Analysis

This study utilized a comprehensive approach to analyze the Quality Management System (QMS) practices among HEIs in Region XII. To assess the extent of QMS practices, key dimensions such as leadership, strategic planning, customer focus, measurement, analysis and knowledge management, workforce focus, operations focus, and organizational performance results were examined. The weighted mean was calculated for each indicator, with results interpreted using a predefined scale.

A comparative analysis across these dimensions revealed areas of strength and opportunities for improvement, contributing valuable insights for policy development. All statistical analyses were conducted at a 5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used to assess the normality of the data sets, which were found not to be normally distributed. Consequently, nonparametric tests were employed for inferential analysis.

The Mann-Whitney U-Test was applied to determine significant differences in QMS practices across respondent groups, while the Kruskal-Wallis Test was used to examine differences in perceptions of QMS practices among deans, faculty members, and students. This rigorous quantitative analysis provided a solid foundation for understanding QMS implementation and performance across HEIs in Region XII, offering actionable insights for institutional improvement.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were a fundamental aspect of this study, ensuring that the research was conducted with integrity and respect for all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the research's purpose, potential risks, and benefits. This helped to ensure that their participation was voluntary and made with full knowledge of the study's objectives. Confidentiality was prioritized, with participant data anonymized and securely stored to protect privacy and sensitive information.

Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. The researcher took steps to minimize any risks and ensured that the study did not cause harm, whether physical or emotional, to those involved. The research was conducted impartially, free from biases or discriminatory practices that could affect the results. Transparency was maintained throughout the process, with clear documentation of research methodologies, data collection procedures, and analysis techniques to ensure the study could be replicated.

The researcher disclosed any potential conflicts of interest that might affect objectivity and adhered to ethical standards by appropriately citing and crediting the work of others, preventing plagiarism. Ethical approval was obtained from the Mindanao State University-Institutional Evaluation and Review Committee before the research commenced. The principle of beneficence was also emphasized, ensuring that the research would offer benefits to the participating universities and colleges in Region XII by improving their QMS practices and overall performance.

Throughout the research process, honesty and integrity were maintained, with transparency in authorship and contributions when publishing the dissertation. These ethical principles were the cornerstone of responsible research and ensured the study adhered to the highest ethical standards from beginning to end.

Results and Discussion

Quality Management System Dimension of Higher Education Institutions

The first research problem deals with the extent of practice of QMS of public and private HEIs in dimensions of leadership, strategic planning, customer focus, measurement, analysis, and knowledge management, workforce focus, operations focus, and organization performance results as perceived by deans, faculty, and students.

Table 1 revealed the perceived extent of quality management system (QMS) practices in the leadership dimension highlights notable differences between private and public higher education institutions (HEIs). In private HEIs, deans rated the continuous review of organizational performance the highest (mean = 4.38, Great Extent), emphasizing their strong commitment to maintaining quality standards and accountability, consistent with principles of strategic leadership and organizational effectiveness (Khan et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2023). However, fostering open communication with staff and faculty received a slightly lower rating (mean = 4.06, Great Extent), suggesting an opportunity to enhance collaboration and shared decision-making within the academic hierarchy (Hakanen et al., 2019; Tran et al., 2019).

Faculty members in private HEIs prioritized ethical behavior monitoring (mean = 4.34, Great Extent), reflecting their dedication to fostering integrity and trust within institutional operations (Polatcan et al., 2023). Conversely, their lesser emphasis on anticipating public concerns (mean = 4.14, Great Extent) underscores the need for deeper engagement with external stakeholders, which could better align institutional offerings with community expectations (McKay, 2018). Students in private HEIs placed the highest value on strategic planning and communication (mean = 4.58, Great Extent), indicating strong support for visionary leadership aligned with their educational needs (Bolman & Deal, 2017). They also recognized the importance of addressing employee challenges during

innovation (mean = 4.46, Great Extent), emphasizing the role of a supportive organizational climate in fostering growth and adaptation (Ahmad et al., 2017).

In public HEIs, deans rated creating strategic directions and effectively communicating vision, mission, and goals the highest (mean = 4.75, Very Great Extent), reflecting transformational leadership principles focused on inspiring and aligning stakeholders (Lee et al., 2023). They also emphasized addressing challenges during innovation (mean = 4.75, Very Great Extent), showcasing proactive problem-solving and a commitment to continuous improvement. Faculty in public HEIs rated communication highly (mean = 4.44, Great Extent), demonstrating its importance for collaboration and supportive work environments (Hakanen et al., 2019). However, they noted a slightly lower emphasis on ethical monitoring (mean = 4.30, Great Extent), signaling the need for stronger ethical frameworks (Polatcan et al., 2023). Students also highly valued strategic vision and mission communication (mean = 4.51, Very Great Extent), underscoring the role of student engagement in institutional success (Aithal & Maiya, 2023).

As a whole, public HEIs exhibited higher leadership-related QMS practices (mean = 4.48) compared to private HEIs (mean = 4.32). This disparity likely reflects the heightened regulatory requirements and public accountability faced by public HEIs (Petersen et al., 2019). Meanwhile, private HEIs, with greater operational flexibility, may prioritize innovation and student experience over formalized QMS practices (Goh & Wong, 2019). These findings highlight differences in organizational culture and leadership development between public and private institutions, where public HEIs focus on compliance and transparency, and private HEIs adopt a more adaptive approach (Brown, 2018). Enhancing leadership communication, ethical monitoring, and stakeholder engagement can further strengthen institutional quality across both sectors, emphasizing the need for tailored leadership strategies that balance compliance, innovation, and accountability.

Table 1. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Leadership as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. Create strategic directions and communicate clear vision, mission, and goals.	4.25 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.37 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.38 (GE)	4.51 (VGE)	4.55 (VGE)
2. Practice continuous and open communication with staff and faculty.	4.06 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.52 (VGE)	4.25 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.44 (GE)	4.43 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)
3. Show appreciation when employees take initiatives to actively contribute to organization development.	4.13 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.49 (GE)
4. Give attention to problems that employees encounter when implementing innovations.	4.13 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.41 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)
5. Continuously review organizational performance.	4.38 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.40 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.36 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.42 (GE)
6. Support performance evaluation by feedback and survey data from faculty and staff.	4.19 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.34 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.47 (GE)
7. Address the impact of school programs and curricular offerings on society.	4.19 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.57 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.38 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.47 (GE)
8. Anticipate public's concern with progress and offerings.	4.25 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.40 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.48 (GE)
9. Establish clear measures to monitor ethical behavior of students, faculty and staff.	4.13 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.56 (VGE)	4.34 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.43 (GE)
10. Portray as role models when it comes to public responsibility and ethics.	4.13 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.36 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.48 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.18 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.52 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.70 (VGE)	4.37 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.48 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 2 revealed the notable differences in the perceived extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in strategic planning between stakeholders in private and public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Region XII. Private HEIs received high ratings from deans, faculty, and students for proactive planning and resource allocation, with deans emphasizing studies and performance measures (mean score: 4.19) and students highlighting proactive planning efforts (mean score: 4.53). These scores reflect a strong institutional commitment to strategic foresight and sustainability, aligning with strategic leadership principles (Jiang et al., 2020). However, gaps in competitive analysis and performance monitoring (mean scores of 3.94 and 4.03, respectively) suggest opportunities to enhance strategic awareness and data-driven decision-making, potentially through investments in analytics tools and training (Power, 2015; Pappas, 2018). Faculty in private HEIs showed particular sensitivity to internal and external dynamics (mean score: 4.28), underscoring their crucial role in shaping strategic initiatives (Rodrigues & Franco, 2019).

In public HEIs, stakeholders consistently rated QMS practices in strategic planning higher than their private counterparts, averaging 4.42 compared to 4.25. Deans in public HEIs prioritized alignment with student learning and development (mean score: 4.75),

indicating a student-centered strategic focus, consistent with research advocating for holistic student growth (Robinson et al., 2008; Virtanen & Tynjälä, 2019). Faculty emphasized competitiveness and academic leadership (mean score: 4.39), while students valued institutional adaptability and foresight (mean score: 4.37). Nevertheless, the slightly lower scores in continuous assessment and strategic analysis (mean scores: 4.23 and 4.25, respectively) reveal areas for improvement in integrating evaluation mechanisms and engaging stakeholders in strategic discussions (Rodrigues & Franco, 2019; David & Abukari, 2019).

Overall, the findings highlight that public HEIs demonstrate a more robust strategic planning framework, benefiting from systemic advantages such as resource availability and regulatory alignment (Kho & Tan, 2015; Altbach et al., 2019). Conversely, private HEIs leverage flexibility and innovation, offering potential for dynamic adaptation despite resource limitations (Teixeira et al., 2017). Both sectors can enhance institutional responsiveness and sustainability by addressing identified gaps in strategic awareness, performance monitoring, and stakeholder engagement.

Table 2. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Strategic Planning as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school management performs studies to identify the factors that affect the organization's future.	4.19 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.37 (GE)	4.44 (GE)
2. The school management undertakes the strategic development process taking into account the school's competitors, weaknesses, and strengths.	3.94 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.22 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.34 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
3. The school management ensures that the strategic objectives are aimed at developing a competitive leadership position in our educational offerings.	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.52 (VGE)	4.25 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.39 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.45 (GE)
4. The school management ensures that the strategic objectives address both short and long-term challenges and opportunity.	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.34 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.44 (GE)
5. The school management ensures that the strategic plan addresses student learning and development	4.13 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.52 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.71 (VGE)	4.35(GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.46 (GE)
6. The school management translates strategic plans into specific requirements for each work unit or department hence greater involvement is attained	4.00 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.22 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.32(GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
7. The school management allocates necessary resources for carrying out these action plans.	4.19 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.40 (GE)
8. The school management uses key measures and indicators in tracking progress relative to action plans.	4.00 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.75 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.43 (GE)
9. The school management uses established key measures or indicators to performance projection.	4.19 (GE)	4.03 (GE)	4.51 (VGE)	4.24 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.40 (GE)
10. The school management continuously assesses progress relative to the action plans.	4.06 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.23 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.36 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.09 (GE)	4.16 (GE)	4.49 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.42 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 3 highlight the perceived extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in the customer focus dimension among deans, faculty, and students in private and public HEIs in Region XII.

In private HEIs, deans rated stakeholder engagement efforts with a mean score of 4.19, described as Great Extent, underscoring a strong institutional commitment to building relationships, leveraging modern complaint mechanisms, and supporting community initiatives. These practices align with the principles of stakeholder theory, emphasizing the role of feedback and transparency in fostering trust and satisfaction (Freeman, 2022). However, areas such as creating a conducive learning climate and using stakeholder feedback for program assessments received lower ratings (mean score: 3.94), indicating room for improvement in aligning institutional strategies with best practices in learning and trust-building (Lee, 2015).

Faculty in private HEIs prioritized community support (mean score: 4.17), reflecting their recognition of the reciprocal benefits of community engagement, such as enhanced research and practical learning opportunities (Epstein, 2018). Despite this strong emphasis, mechanisms for determining students' needs were rated 4.00, suggesting existing efforts require further development to ensure comprehensive and responsive approaches. Addressing these gaps could involve systematic feedback collection, improved communication channels, and targeted resource allocation to enhance stakeholder satisfaction and retention (Carpentier & Mageau, 2013; Silva et al., 2016).

Students in private HEIs highly valued the institution’s community engagement, assigning a mean score of 4.50 (Very Great Extent) for efforts supporting key communities. This appreciation highlights the importance of integrating community service into educational experiences to foster civic responsibility and personal growth (Bringle et al., 2020). However, the relatively lower score of 4.35 for mechanisms addressing student needs points to opportunities for more robust systems that actively capture and respond to student feedback, aligning services with their expectations (Seale, 2015).

Overall, private HEIs demonstrate a strong commitment to stakeholder engagement and social responsibility, with areas for improvement in learning climate, stakeholder feedback utilization, and mechanisms for addressing student needs. Bridging these gaps could lead to enhanced trust, satisfaction, and long-term institutional success through continuous improvement and innovation in customer-focused practices.

Table 3. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Customer Focus as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school management has well- established mechanism for determining students’ needs and expectations.	4.06 (GE)	4.00 (GE)	4.39 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.44 (GE)
2. The school management has created a climate conducive to learning.	3.94 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.18 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.33 (GE)
3. The school management ensures educational programs are dynamic and keep pace with market changes.	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.21 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.34 (GE)
4. The school management uses feedback from our stakeholders to assess our programs and offerings.	3.94 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.19 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
5. The school management continuously builds and sustains active relationships with students and stakeholders.	4.19 (GE)	4.07 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
6. The school management has modern mechanism for students/stakeholders to make complaints about our programs/services.	4.19 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.41 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
7. The school management has established effective mechanism for determining students/stakeholders’ satisfaction/dissatisfaction.	4.19 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.43 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.27 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
8. The school management has well established mechanism for determining students’ needs and expectations.	4.00 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.16 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.25 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.35 (GE)
9. The school management supports key communities and other public purposes	4.19 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.35 (GE)
10. The school management sustains high trust of the stakeholders.	3.94 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.36 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.43 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.08 (GE)	4.11 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.39 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 4 highlight the perceived extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in the measurement, analysis, and knowledge management dimension across public and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII. Both types of institutions demonstrate a strong commitment to customer-focused practices, with public HEIs exhibiting slightly higher scores (4.39) compared to private HEIs (4.23). This suggests that public HEIs, benefiting from stricter regulations, greater funding, and a mission centered on public service, are more effectively implementing these practices.

Public HEIs excel in areas such as stakeholder satisfaction and feedback mechanisms, with a particularly high mean score (4.67) for determining satisfaction and dissatisfaction among students and stakeholders. This indicates a robust system for continuous improvement through active feedback, which enhances student retention and success (Seale, 2015; Fried, 2023). However, while public HEIs maintain strong relationships with stakeholders (mean score of 4.46), there is room for improvement in the consistency and effectiveness of engagement activities, suggesting a need for more structured outreach efforts (Kotler & Fox, 1995; Seale, 2015). Additionally, faculty members in public HEIs have a positive perception of the institution’s trust-building efforts, with a score of 4.36, reflecting confidence in institutional decision-making and communication (Lee, 2015; Smith & Brown, 2018).

In terms of creating a conducive learning environment, public HEIs scored 4.18, highlighting opportunities for further improvements in infrastructure, faculty development, and academic culture to enhance the learning experience (Kezar & Maxey, 2014; Freeman, 2022). Students also rated the effectiveness of mechanisms to assess their needs and expectations highly (4.36), which underscores the success of public HEIs in integrating student feedback into institutional decisions (Al-Omari & Al-Khawaldeh, 2022; Fried, 2023).

However, both faculty and students indicated that there is still room for improvement in creating a more supportive learning environment, with scores of 4.24 for creating a climate conducive to learning.

Private HEIs, while performing well in customer-focused practices, received slightly lower scores in some areas, reflecting challenges related to operational flexibility, market pressures, and resource availability (Elken, 2020). Faculty in private HEIs particularly valued community support but noted areas for improvement in fostering a climate conducive to learning and utilizing stakeholder feedback. These institutions might benefit from a more structured approach to stakeholder engagement and investment in faculty and resource development to enhance the learning environment.

Overall, both public and private HEIs are committed to customer-focused QMS practices, but public HEIs appear to have a more substantial implementation due to their regulatory environment and mission-driven focus on public service. These findings underscore the importance of continuous feedback systems, stakeholder engagement, and a strong commitment to improving the learning environment to enhance institutional performance and student satisfaction.

Table 4. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Measurement, Analysis, and Knowledge Management as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school management uses data and information for tracking overall organization performance.	4.25 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.31 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.47 (GE)
2. The school management obtains data and information by benchmarking and seeking competitive comparisons.	4.00 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.16 (GE)	4.16 (GE)	4.32 (GE)
3. The school management performance analysis that help determine root causes and set priorities for reasonable use.	4.19 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.49 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.27 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.32 (GE)
4. The school management conducts performance analysis that includes examining trends.	4.00 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.19 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.20 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.35 (GE)
5. The school management has information systems that are standardized across departments.	4.06 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.21 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
6. The school management ensures that hardware and software are reliable, secured, and user-friendly.	4.06 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.27 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.20 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.33 (GE)
7. The school management ensures that organization knowledge system focuses on its identification and sharing of best practices.	4.19 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.43 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
8. The school management ensures that people keep current with changing educational needs and directions.	4.00 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.25 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.34 (GE)
9. The school management collects and integrates information on evidence of student.	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.24 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
10. The school management learning conducts performance analysis drawn from all types of data encompassing all programs, stakeholders, market, operational, budgetary.	4.06 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.19 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.09 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.39 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 5 highlight the perceived extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices of Workforce Focus dimension across public and private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII. The findings of this study highlight the importance of data-driven decision-making and quality management systems (QMS) in both private and public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII, with notable emphasis on data usage, benchmarking, and performance analysis.

In private HEIs, deans rated the use of data for tracking organizational performance highly (mean score of 4.25), indicating a strong commitment to evidence-based decision-making. This focus on data helps institutions align their actions with goals and improve organizational effectiveness (Tambare et al., 2021). However, the lower mean score of 4.00 for benchmarking and performance analysis suggests that there are challenges in consistently utilizing these practices to their full potential. Improvements are needed in implementing systematic benchmarking and performance analysis to optimize decision-making and institutional effectiveness (Paliulis & Labanuskis, 2015). Faculty members also valued the reliability and security of technology (mean score of 4.31), underscoring the role of robust technological infrastructure in enhancing educational delivery and safeguarding information (Kho, 2015; Iqbal, 2021). Nevertheless, their rating of 4.10 for benchmarking, performance analysis, and staff development suggests a need for more comprehensive and systematic approaches to these practices (Oakland, 2014; Deming, 2018). Students in private HEIs expressed strong approval of data usage for performance tracking (mean score of 4.50), recognizing its role in enhancing their educational experience.

However, their slightly lower score of 4.38 for performance analysis points to areas for improvement in the depth and transparency of the analysis (Neyestani & Juanzon, 2017).

In public HEIs, deans rated data integration for student performance highly (mean score of 4.67), demonstrating a commitment to continuous improvement and evidence-based strategies (Tambare et al., 2021). However, the slightly lower score of 4.46 for performance analysis indicates that more effective use of data to determine root causes and set priorities is needed (Dong, 2023). Faculty members in public HEIs also rated the use of data for tracking performance highly (mean score of 4.45), emphasizing the importance of continuous improvement in institutional effectiveness (Korthals, 2020; Rubel & Jones, 2017). However, benchmarking received a lower score of 4.16, suggesting that public HEIs may need to enhance their use of external comparisons to inform strategic decision-making (Paliulis & Labanauskis, 2015). Students in public HEIs similarly valued data-driven decision-making (mean score of 4.45) but rated benchmarking practices lower (mean score of 4.16), indicating areas for improvement in utilizing external data for institutional improvement (Tasopoulou & Tsiotras, 2017).

Overall, public HEIs exhibited a higher mean score of 4.39 for QMS practices compared to private HEIs (4.22), suggesting that public institutions may have more resources and a stronger regulatory environment to support quality management (Sattler, 2018). These findings underscore the critical role of data integration, performance analysis, and benchmarking in driving continuous improvement and ensuring the effectiveness and competitiveness of higher education institutions.

Table 5. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Workforce Focus as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school effectively organizes and manages work and jobs to promote empowerment and innovation.	4.19 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
2. The school provides a work system that ensures on going education and training for the employees.	4.06 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.22 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.49 (GE)	4.27 (GE)	4.48 (GE)
3. The school uses a performance management system that includes feedback to employees.	4.19 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
4. The school implements a compensation and recognition approaches that include rewarding exemplary performance.	4.00 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.20 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.36 (GE)
5. The school uses an effective way of recruiting and hiring employees.	4.06 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.24 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.23 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.34 (GE)
6. The school effective career progression for all administrative and technical staff throughout the organization.	3.94 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.20 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.36 (GE)
7. The school employees' education and training program that addresses out key needs associated with the organization performance management and technological change.	4.06 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.49 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.37 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
8. The school reinforces the use of new knowledge and skills obtained by employees on the job.	3.94 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.41 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
9. The school implements effective ways in motivating employees to develop their well-being, satisfaction, motivation, and utilize their full potential	4.25 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
10. The school provides many opportunities for employees' professional development, services, and benefits	3.88 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.12 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.23 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.36 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.06 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.22 (GE)	4.55 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.39 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 6 showed the analysis of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in private and public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Region XII reveals notable strengths and areas for improvement. Private HEIs demonstrated strong commitment to operational dimensions such as process analysis, benchmarking, clientele review, and research, with deans rating their efforts at a mean score of 4.19 ("Great Extent"). These practices enhance efficiency, service quality, and stakeholder alignment, supported by Bryson (2018) and Paliulis and Labanauskis (2015). However, challenges in faculty preparedness for delivering Learning-Centered Processes (LCP), rated at 3.88 by private HEI faculty, highlight gaps in professional development and resource allocation. This aligns with Solomon et al. (2023) and Fullan (2020), who emphasize the critical role of faculty training in effective instruction.

Public HEIs outperformed private HEIs in QMS practices, with deans rating the implementation of LCP and Support Processes (SP)

at 4.67 ("Very Great Extent"). These practices prioritize holistic student development and adaptive learning, resonating with Carpentier and Mageau's (2013) findings on active learning. Continuous improvement in SPs reflects institutional agility, consistent with Smith and Brown's (2018) change management principles. Public HEIs also scored higher in aligning work processes with organizational goals, rated by students and faculty at 4.42 and 4.32, respectively, underscoring their effectiveness in strategic integration, as noted by Hazelkorn (2018).

Students in both private and public HEIs highlighted the importance of technology integration, rating it highest at 4.53 ("Very Great Extent"), emphasizing its role in enhancing educational outcomes and administrative efficiency (Means et al., 2016; Picciano, 2018). However, slightly lower scores for SP implementation (4.43) in public HEIs suggest occasional lapses in service quality, warranting improvement in delivery mechanisms (Klemenčič, 2017; Seale, 2015). Both private and public HEIs demonstrate a commitment to quality, but targeted enhancements in faculty development, resource allocation, and consistent implementation of SPs are essential for sustained success. These findings highlight the importance of refining strategic alignment, advancing performance measurement practices, and fostering faculty preparedness to ensure continuous improvement and student satisfaction.

Table 6. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in dimension of Operation Focus as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school designs the work processes in line with the organization's goals and competencies.	4.06 (GE)	4.03 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.20 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
2. The school uses learning- centered process (LCP) that addresses student educational and developmental needs to maximize their success.	3.94 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.20 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.31 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.45 (GE)
3. The school uses effective key LCP that delivers educational programs and offerings	4.00 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.21 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.28 (GE)	4.38 (GE)
4. The school ensures that the faculty members properly prepared to deliver the LCP.	3.88 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.41 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
5. The school incorporates new technology and organizational knowledge into the design of the LCP and support processes (SP).	4.00 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.21 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.21 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
6. The school uses key performance measures for the control, and improvement of the LCP and SP.	4.06 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.18 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.33 (GE)
7. The school performs process analysis, conducts benchmarking, clientele review, and research in improving processes.	4.19 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.29 (GE)	4.40 (GE)
8. The school implements effective ways in determining and ensuring the key SPs	4.00 (GE)	4.03 (GE)	4.43 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.19 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.32 (GE)
9. The school continuously improves the SPs to achieve better performance and to keep current with organizational needs	4.00 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.51 (VGE)	4.24 (GE)	4.67 (VGE)	4.25 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.42 (GE)
10. The school shares successful strategies across the whole organization	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.35 (GE)	4.42 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.03 (GE)	4.13 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.39 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 7 revealed the results on the perceived extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in the Organizational Performance Results dimension among deans, faculty, and students in both private and public HEIs in Region XII.

In private HEIs, deans rated satisfaction with student learning outcomes, stakeholder trust, and financial resource management at a mean score of 4.13 ("Great Extent"), suggesting effective systems for curriculum design, stakeholder feedback integration, and financial management. These factors contribute to favorable learning outcomes and operational sustainability (Fried, 2023; Pather et al., 2022). However, the score of 3.94 for stakeholder trust indicates a need to enhance transparency and accountability measures to strengthen engagement (Beerkens & Udam, 2017). Faculty rated stakeholder feedback incorporation highly (4.17), demonstrating strong responsiveness and a commitment to continuous improvement, which cultivates a student-centered environment and enhances institutional reputation (Fried, 2023). Students rated timeliness in educational and student support services at 4.53 ("Very Great Extent"), reflecting efforts to prioritize efficiency and service quality. However, the lower score of 4.00 for satisfaction with referrals and recommendations suggests room for improvement in leveraging feedback for reputation-building and marketing (Freeman, 2018).

In public HEIs, financial management received a high rating of 4.38 ("Great Extent"), signifying effective stewardship of resources, though improvements in transparency and reporting could address concerns (Altbach et al., 2019). The perception that feedback mechanisms effectively inform institutional practices scored 4.63 ("Very Great Extent"), showcasing a robust culture of stakeholder engagement and responsiveness. This highlights the importance of feedback-driven strategies for maintaining educational quality and

institutional success (Pather et al., 2022).

Comparing private and public HEIs, public institutions achieved a slightly higher overall mean score (4.38) compared to private institutions (4.20). This suggests that public HEIs may have more robust organizational performance practices, likely influenced by differences in resource allocation, accountability measures, and institutional priorities (Shrouf et al., 2020; Spekle & Verbeeten, 2014). Both sectors demonstrated a commitment to stakeholder feedback and responsiveness, with room for improvement in stakeholder trust-building, transparency in financial management, and leveraging positive referrals.

To enhance institutional effectiveness, private HEIs should focus on building trust, optimizing referrals, and enhancing employee satisfaction. Public HEIs, while performing well, could benefit from refining financial management practices and maintaining high stakeholder satisfaction through continuous monitoring and targeted initiatives. Both sectors must align QMS practices with emerging educational trends and stakeholder expectations, fostering a culture of continuous improvement. This will ensure the long-term success of both private and public HEIs, reinforcing their commitment to meeting and exceeding stakeholder expectations.

Table 7. Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs in Dimension of Organization Performance Results as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Indicators	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean n=16	Faculty n=29	Student n=96	Mean n=141	Dean n=24	Faculty n=250	Student n=255	Mean n=529
1. The school performance results reveal that organization is satisfied with the student learning results.	4.13 (GE)	4.03 (GE)	4.51 (VGE)	4.22 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.44 (GE)
2. The school performance results reveal that students and stakeholders had positive referrals and recommendations of the school services.	4.06 (GE)	4.00 (GE)	4.48 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.35 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.42 (GE)
3. The school performance results reveal that students and stakeholders had high regard for its organization.	4.13 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.36 (GE)
4. The school performance results reveal that feedback from students and stakeholders on their assessment of the educational operations are being heard of.	4.06 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.39 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.40 (GE)
5. The school performance results reveal that the organization manages its financial resources very well.	4.13 (GE)	4.07 (GE)	4.43 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.31 (GE)
6. The school performance results reveal that the market is satisfied with its services they receive from the organization.	4.06 (GE)	4.10 (GE)	4.38 (GE)	4.18 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.38 (GE)
7. The school performance results reveal that the organization is creating and maintaining positive and productive environment for employees.	4.00 (GE)	4.07 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
8. The school performance results reveal that the employees have improved levels of satisfaction.	4.00 (GE)	4.07 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.17 (GE)	4.42 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.27 (GE)	4.31 (GE)
9. The school performance results reveal that The organization is experiencing improvement in timeliness in all key areas of educational and student support areas	4.06 (GE)	4.14 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.24 (GE)	4.54 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
10. The school performance results reveal that the stakeholders have high trust in the organization.	3.94 (GE)	4.03 (GE)	4.50 (VGE)	4.16 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.30 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.41 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.06 (GE)	4.08 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.20 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.38 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

Table 8 revealed the practice of Quality Management Systems (QMS) across private and public higher education institutions (HEIs) in Region XII, as perceived by deans, faculty, and students, reveals a high level of commitment to QMS practices across all evaluated dimensions. In terms of Leadership, both private and public HEIs demonstrated a strong adherence to leadership practices, with public HEIs scoring slightly higher (4.48) compared to private HEIs (4.32). This difference suggests that public institutions may have more formalized leadership structures, possibly due to larger resources and a stronger emphasis on accountability, although both sectors exhibit a commendable commitment to leadership.

When it comes to Strategic Planning, public HEIs scored higher (4.42) than private HEIs (4.25), indicating that public institutions may place more emphasis on strategic planning, potentially driven by regulatory requirements, greater resources, and larger organizational scales. However, both types of institutions show a robust implementation of strategic planning practices, underscoring their dedication to long-term institutional goals. Regarding Customer Focus, public HEIs again scored higher (4.39) compared to private HEIs (4.21), suggesting that public institutions may prioritize student and stakeholder satisfaction more heavily due to public accountability and

broader mandates. Nevertheless, private institutions also perform well in this dimension, driven by competitive market forces aimed at student retention and satisfaction.

In the dimension of Measurement, Analysis, and Knowledge Management, public HEIs (4.37) again outscored private HEIs (4.23), likely due to the more structured and systematic approaches required by regulatory measures, greater resource allocation, and a focus on transparency. Both sectors, however, demonstrate effective and consistent implementation of these practices, contributing to informed decision-making and continuous improvement. For Workforce Focus, public HEIs scored higher (4.39) compared to private HEIs (4.22), which can be attributed to the more structured workforce development programs and government support available to public institutions. Still, private institutions also show significant commitment to workforce development, satisfaction, and performance, despite potentially fewer resources.

In the Operation Focus dimension, public HEIs (4.39) again had a higher score than private HEIs (4.21), reflecting a more systematic approach to operational management in public institutions, which may benefit from larger budgets and regulatory oversight. However, private HEIs also exhibit strong operational practices, ensuring efficient resource management and service delivery.

Lastly, in terms of Organizational Performance Results, public HEIs scored higher (4.38) than private HEIs (4.20), possibly due to the larger resource base and broader missions of public institutions. Nonetheless, both types of institutions demonstrate strong organizational performance, contributing to positive outcomes in key areas such as student learning, stakeholder satisfaction, and financial management.

In conclusion, while public HEIs tend to score slightly higher across most dimensions, both private and public HEIs in Region XII show a strong commitment to implementing QMS practices. This widespread adoption of QMS frameworks across both sectors highlights a shared dedication to ensuring operational excellence, continuous improvement, and meeting the needs of stakeholders. Both types of institutions, despite their differences in resources and scale, demonstrate a commendable level of adherence to QMS principles, ensuring their success and advancement in higher education.

Table 8. Summary on Extent of Practice of QMS among Private and Public HEIs as Perceived by Dean, Faculty, and Students

Quality Management System Dimensions	Private HEI				Public HEI (SUC)			
	Dean	Faculty	Student	Mean	Dean	Faculty	Student	Mean
1. Leadership	4.18 (GE)	4.26 (GE)	4.52 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.70 (VGE)	4.37 (GE)	4.36 (GE)	4.48 (GE)
2. Strategic Planning	4.09 (GE)	4.16 (GE)	4.49 (GE)	4.25 (GE)	4.63 (VGE)	4.32 (GE)	4.31 (GE)	4.42 (GE)
3. Customer Focus	4.08 (GE)	4.11 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.28 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
4. Measurement, Analysis and Knowledge Management	4.09 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.45 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.55 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.30 (GE)	4.37 (GE)
5. Workforce Focus	4.06 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.44 (GE)	4.22 (GE)	4.55 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.34 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
6. Operations Focus	4.03 (GE)	4.13 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.21 (GE)	4.58 (VGE)	4.26 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.39 (GE)
7. Organization Performance Results	4.06 (GE)	4.08 (GE)	4.46 (GE)	4.20 (GE)	4.53 (VGE)	4.27 (GE)	4.33 (GE)	4.38 (GE)
Overall Mean	4.08 (GE)	4.15 (GE)	4.47 (GE)	4.23 (GE)	4.59 (VGE)	4.29 (GE)	4.32 (GE)	4.40 (GE)

Legend: 4.50-5.00-Very Great Extent (VGE) 3.50-4.49-Great Extent (GE) 2.50-3.49-Moderate Extent (ME) 1.50-2.49-Less Extent (LE) 1.00-1.49-Least Extent (LTE)

The table 9 presents the results of a comparative analysis of Quality Management System (QMS) practices between private and public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Region XII. The analysis revealed no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of QMS practices in the two categories. This finding, supported by both p-value and U-statistic analysis, indicates that the extent of QMS practice is comparable across both private and public HEIs in the region.

This outcome aligns with existing literature that highlights the shared aspirations and distinct challenges faced by both types of institutions. While private HEIs enjoy greater autonomy and flexibility, they also face competitive pressures and market demands. Public HEIs, on the other hand, operate within a more regulated environment with constraints related to government policies and funding limitations. Despite these contextual differences, both types of institutions are committed to delivering quality education and maintaining high standards, prioritizing stakeholder expectations and continuous improvement.

The implication of this finding is that both private and public HEIs should continue to prioritize the implementation and continuous improvement of QMS initiatives, regardless of their institutional category. Collaboration between these institutions in sharing best practices and lessons learned could further enhance overall quality standards across the higher education sector. By acknowledging and addressing the unique needs and circumstances of each institution while remaining mindful of overarching quality benchmarks and standards, HEIs can effectively navigate their respective contexts and contribute to a more cohesive and effective higher education landscape.

Table 9. *Difference in the QMS Practices between Private and Public HEIs in Region XII*

HEI Category	Mean	Mean Ranks	U-value	p-value	Remark	Decision
Private	4.36	49705.5				Accept null hypothesis
Public	4.32	175079.5	39694.5	0.2387	Not Significant	

*Tested at 0.05 level of significance

Table 10 showed the analysis comparing the perceptions of deans, faculty, and students regarding the extent of Quality Management System (QMS) practices in HEIs in Region XII revealed no statistically significant differences among the groups. While slight variations in mean scores were observed, with deans rating QMS practices slightly higher than faculty and students, these differences were not statistically significant.

This finding suggests that despite potential differences in perspectives due to their roles and experiences within the institution, deans, faculty, and students generally share a similar understanding of the extent to which QMS practices are implemented and effective within their respective HEIs. This implies a shared perception of the strengths and weaknesses of the institution's quality management efforts.

The implication of this result for QMS practices is that it highlights the importance of considering multiple stakeholder perspectives when assessing and improving quality standards in HEIs. While deans, faculty, and students may have varying viewpoints, their collective feedback and input are invaluable for enhancing overall quality management efforts. By fostering open communication channels and mechanisms for soliciting feedback from all stakeholders, HEIs can ensure that QMS initiatives address their needs and expectations comprehensively. Furthermore, this result underscores the significance of continuous engagement and dialogue among stakeholders to build consensus and alignment towards shared quality goals. By promoting a culture of transparency, inclusivity, and collaboration, HEIs can strengthen their QMS practices and drive continuous improvement efforts that benefit the entire academic community.

Table 10. *Difference in QMS Practices among HEIs in Region XII as Perceived by Deans, Faculty and Students*

Groups	Mean	Mean Rank	H-value	p-value	Remark	Decision
Deans	4.39	359.54				Accept Null Hypothesis
Faculty	4.28	319.93	3.3100	0.1911	Not Significant	
Students	4.36	345.13				

*Tested at 0.05 level of significance

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that both private and public higher education institutions (HEIs) demonstrate a high level of adherence to implementing quality practices substantially and consistently. This indicates that the majority of instances or situations within these institutions involve the effective application of these practices, reflecting their commitment to upholding quality standards. Such consistency suggests that HEIs have successfully integrated quality management principles into their operations, supported by effective dissemination of policies and training. This widespread and reliable implementation highlights the institutions' dedication to maintaining and enhancing their performance and achieving their educational goals.

Moreover, the study reveals that Quality Management System (QMS) practices are generally uniform across HEIs, regardless of whether they are private or public or the specific respondent groups involved, such as administrators, faculty, or staff. This uniformity can be attributed to the standardized guidelines and frameworks established by regulatory and accrediting bodies, which are effectively adopted across the sector. The alignment of internal institutional policies with these external standards fosters a shared culture of accountability and excellence. Furthermore, the consistency in QMS practices reflects an equitable approach to quality assurance, ensuring that all institutions and stakeholders have access to similar resources and support systems. This not only minimizes disparities but also promotes collaboration, benchmarking, and the exchange of best practices, enabling HEIs to address challenges collectively while pursuing continuous improvement.

References

- Abbas, J., & Kumari, K. (2023). Examining the relationship between total quality management and knowledge management and their impact on organizational performance: a dimensional analysis. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 39(2), 426–451. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeas-03-2021-0046>
- Aboudahr, S. M. F. M. (2022). The relationship between strategic leadership, organizational climate and quality management practices in Egypt public universities. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 4, 1-21. https://etd.uum.edu.my/9731/2/s903528_01.pdf
- Administrative Order No. 161 series of 2005.
- Ahmad, A. F., & Karadas, G. (2021). Managers' perceptions regarding the effect of leadership on organizational performance: mediating role of green supply chain management practices. *Sage Open*, 11(2), 21582440211018686. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211018686>

- Aithal, P. S., & Maiya, A. K. (2023). Development of a New Conceptual Model for Improvement of the Quality Services of Higher Education Institutions in Academic, Administrative, and Research Areas. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 8(4), 260-308. <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMTS.2581.6012.0322>
- Alaghbari, M. A., Al-Dubai, M. M., & Arishi, N. A. S. (2022). The Relationship between Total Quality Management and Organizational Performance. *Information Sciences Letters*, 11(1), 199–207. <https://doi.org/10.18576/isl/110121>
- Albaqami, S. (2015). Quality concepts: Perceptions of stakeholders at two Saudi Arabian universities. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 5(5), 59-69. <https://bit.ly/3xt5sVP>
- Al-Dajani, E. A., & Abedulaal, S. (2018). Enhancing the Role of Palestinian Universities Higher Management in Quality Assurance: A Proposed Model. *The Arab Journal For Quality Assurance in Higher Education*, 11(38), 3–27. <https://doi.org/10.20428/ajqahe.v11i38.1428>
- Al-Mohaimed, A. A., & Kadam, A. (2015). Impact of ISO 9001-Based Quality Management System on the Performance of Saudi Arabian Universities. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 23(4), 418-432. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-06-2013-0024>
- Al-Omari, J. Al- Khawaldeh, A.A. (2022). Quality Assurance in Higher Education Institutions.. *Journal of Education and Practice*.13(3). <https://doi.org/10.7176/jep/13-3-04>
- Al-Qahtani, N. D., Alshehri, S. S. A., & Aziz, A. A. (2015). The impact of Total Quality Management on organizational performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(36), 119-127. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234627007.pdf>
- Al-Shammari, H. (2019). Quality Management in Higher Education: An Exploration of the Issues and Challenges in Saudi Universities. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(1), 42-62. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-07-2018-0055>
- Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2019). *Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution*. Brill. <https://brill.com/display/title/36570?languag>
- Ambula, R., Kariuki, A., & Wasike, S. (2017). Knowledge Management and Performance in Manufacturing Firms: The Mediating Role of Learning Organization. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 5(1), 9–28. <https://bit.ly/3xiVAhk>
- Asif, M., & De Vries, H. J. (2014). Total Quality Management & Business Excellence Creating ambidexterity through quality management. *Taylor & Francis*, 26(11–12), 1226–1241. <https://bit.ly/3KKGtjZ>
- AV, N., & Aithal, P. S. (2018). Employability skill traits management quotient [ESMQ]-A conceptual model proposal. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 2(1), 1-30. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3106453>
- Aydin, H., Koseoglu, M. A., & Demirer, V. (2014). Quality Assurance in Higher Education: An Evaluation of the Practices in Turkish Universities. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 19(2), 150-164. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09684881111139440>
- Baran, R. J., & Galka, R. J. (2020). Understanding the Customer–Company Profit Chain: Satisfaction, Loyalty, Retention, and Profits. In *CRM* (pp. 227–248). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203107577-15>
- Beerkens, M., & Udam, M. (2017). Stakeholders in higher education quality assurance: Richness in diversity?. *Higher Education Policy*, 30, 341-359. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-016-0032-6>
- Bolman, L. G., & Deal, T. E. (2017). *Reframing organizations: Artistry, choice, and leadership*. John Wiley & Sons. bit.ly/3XsersL
- Bryson, J. M. (2018). *Strategic planning for public and nonprofit organizations: A guide to strengthening and sustaining organizational achievement*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://bit.ly/3xgETTU>
- Carpentier, J., & Mageau, G. A. (2013). When change-oriented feedback enhances motivation, well-being and performance: A look at autonomy-supportive feedback in sport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 14(3), 423-435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2013.01.003>
- Chaokromthong, K., & Sintao, N. (2021). Sample Size Estimation using Yamane and Cochran and Krejcie and Morgan and Green Formulas and Cohen Statistical Power Analysis by G* Power and Comparisons. *APHEIT International Journal*, 10(2), 76-86. <https://so04.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/ATI/article/view/254253>
- Commission on Higher Education (CHED) No. 1 series of 2005.
- Commission on Higher Education (CHED) No. 46 series of 2012.
- Commission on Higher Education (CHED). (1994). Higher Education Act of 1994. <http://www.ched.gov.ph/higher-education-act-of-1994/>
- David, S. A., & Abukari, A. (2019). Perspectives of teachers’ on the selection and the development of the school leaders in the United Arab Emirates. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(1), 56-69. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-02-2019-0057>

DBM-CHEd Memorandum Circular No. 1, Series of 2016. FY 2016 Levelling Instrument for SUCs and Guidelines for the Implementation Thereof.

Deming, W. E. (2018). *Out of the Crisis*, reissue. MIT press. <https://bit.ly/3VGYuG7>

Dick, G. P., & Tari, J. J. (2013). A review of quality management research in higher education institutions. Kent Business School Working Paper Series, 274. <https://kar.kent.ac.uk/37512/>

Dong, Y. (2023). Teaching Quality Monitoring and Evaluation in Higher Education through a Big Data Analysis. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 18(8), 61–78. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i08.39247>

Elken, M. (2020). Marketing in higher education. In *The International Encyclopedia of Higher Education Systems and Institutions* (pp. 2032-2037). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8905-9_569

El-Moussa, O. J. (2023). The Challenge of Predicting College Success in Male and Female Saudi Arabian Students: An Examination of Whether High School GPA, Qudrat, and Tahsili Are Effective Predictors (Doctoral dissertation, The University of North Dakota). <https://bit.ly/3zdJhDu>

Epstein, J. L. (2018). School, family, and community partnerships in teachers' professional work. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 44(3), 397–406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2018.1465669>

Executive Order No. 605. Institutionalizing QMS in the Government. 2007

Freeman, R. E. (2022). My Own Book Review. *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. *Management*, 25(1). <https://doi.org/10.37725/mgmt.v25.8519>

Fried, J. (2023). Transformative learning through engagement: Student Affairs Practice as Experiential Pedagogy. *Transformative Learning Through Engagement: Student Affairs Practice as Experiential Pedagogy* (pp. 1–200). Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003448303>

Fullan, M. (2020). The Meaning of Educational Change. In *The New Meaning of Educational Change* (pp. 28–41). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203986561-9>

Godoy, M. C. (2019). Status and prospect for sustainable development toward quality and excellence of Batangas State University (Batstateu). *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publication*, 3(3), 104-115. <https://bit.ly/45qjPXw>

Golowko, N., Kopia, J., Geldmacher, W., & Förster-Pastor, U. S. (2017). Comparative Study on Quality Management at German Private Universities. *Quality-access to success*, 18(157). <https://bit.ly/4c49S4y>

González-Cruz, T. F., Roig-Tierno, N., & Botella-Carrubí, D. (2018). Quality management as a driver of innovation in the service industry. *Service Business*, 12(3), 505-524. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11628-017-0360-7>

Hakanen, J. J., Peeters, M. C., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2018). Different types of employee well-being across time and their relationships with job crafting. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 23(2), 289. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000081>

Hakkak, M., Karimian, L., & Mohammadi, M. (2019). The Role of Quality Management System in Improving the Quality of Services Provided by Higher Education Institutions. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(2), 153-170. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-04-2018-0026>

Hazelkorn, E., Coates, H., & McCormick, A. C. (Eds.). (2018). *Research handbook on quality, performance and accountability in higher education*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785369759>

Hietschold, N., Reinhardt, R., & Gurtner, S. (2014). Measuring critical success factors of TQM implementation successfully—a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Production Research*, 52(21), 6254–6272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2014.918288>

Hong, J., Liao, Y., Zhang, Y., & Yu, Z. (2019). The effect of supply chain quality management practices and capabilities on operational and innovation performance: Evidence from Chinese manufacturers. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 212, 227-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.01.036>

Ibrahim, Abaasi, Musenze & Mayende, Sifuna, Thomas | (2020) Development and validation of a total quality management model for Uganda's local governments, *Cogent Business & Management*, 7:1, 1767996, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1767996>

In'airat, M. Hasan., & Kassem, A. H. A.-. (2014). Total Quality Management in Higher Education: A Review. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 294. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v4i3.6368>

International Organization for Standardization. (2015). ISO 9001:2015 - Quality management systems - Requirements.

Iqbal, A. (2021), "Innovation speed and quality in higher education institutions: the role of knowledge management enablers and

knowledge sharing process", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 25 No. 9, pp. 2334-2360. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2020-0546>

ISO 9001:2015. Quality management systems - Requirements. International Organization for Standardization.

Jabbarzare, E., & Shafiqhi, N. (2019). Total Quality Management Practices and Organizational Performance. *Open Science Journal of Statistics and Application*, 6(1), 6–12. <http://www.openscienceonline.com/journal/osjsa>

Jiang, J., Lee, S. K., & Rah, M. J. (2020). Assessing the research efficiency of Chinese higher education institutions by data envelopment analysis. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 21(3), 423-440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-020-09634-0>

Jimoh, R., Oyewobi, L., Isa, R., & Waziri, I. (2019). Total quality management practices and organizational performance: the mediating roles of strategies for continuous improvement. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 19(2), 162–177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2017.1411456>

Kezar, A. & Holcombe, E.,(2018). Mental models and implementing new faculty roles. *Innovative Higher Education*, 43, 91-106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-017-9415-x>

Khan, I., Hasnain, S., Ullah, S., & Khalid, A. (2018). Impact of transformational leadership on employee's job satisfaction and well-being through team efficacy in PMBMC. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 8(1), 327. . <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v8i1.12521>

Khan, M. N., Malik, S. A., & Janjua, S. Y. (2019). Total Quality Management practices and work-related outcomes: A case study of higher education institutions in Pakistan. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 36(6), 864-874. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-04-2018-0097>

Kho, J. C. Y., & Tan, G. W. H. (2015). Strategic planning dimensions for information technology governance. *Journal of Information Technology*, 18(2), 87-92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0268396032000071647>

Klemenčič, M. (2017). From Student Engagement to Student Agency: Conceptual Considerations of European Policies on Student-Centered Learning in Higher Education. *Higher Education Policy*, 30(1), 69-85. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-016-0034-4>

Korbozerova, N., Kopal, V., Resler, M., Veremchuk, O., & Chovriy, S. (2022). Methods for Modelling the Process of Training Future Teachers in the Context of Implementing a Quality Management System in Higher Education Institutions. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 11(3), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jct.v11n3p84>

Korthals, R. A., & Dronkers, J. (2016). Selection on performance and tracking. *Applied Economics*, 48(30), 2836-2851. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2015.1130789>

Kunz, P. (2021). The effects of total quality management practices on firm's performance. <https://bit.ly/3KNDS2c>

Lai, K. Y. (2022). How to adapt international quality assurance approaches to Hong Kong: a diary-based approach to analyse quality assurance approaches of quality assurance bodies. <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi:amk-2022060515434>

Lee, C. Y., & Lee, H. H. (2015). The integrated relationship among organizational learning, TQM and firm's business performance: A structural equation modeling approach. *International Business Research*, 8(5), 43. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v8n5p43>

Lee, J., Loretta Kim, S., & Yun, S. (2023). Encouraging employee voice: coworker knowledge sharing, psychological safety, and promotion focus. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(5), 1044-1069. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2021.2018014>

Lee, V. H., & Ooi, K. B. (2015). Applying the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award criteria: an approach to strengthen organisational memory and process innovation. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 26(11-12), 1373-1386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2014.934519>

Liquido, M. G. E. (2018). The accreditation of state universities and colleges in the Philippines: Governance, hegemony relationship and dichotomy of ownership. <https://bit.ly/3xrsBrG>

Liu, H. C., Liu, R., Gu, X., & Yang, M. (2023, June 1). From total quality management to Quality 4.0: A systematic literature review and future research agenda. *Frontiers of Engineering Management*. Higher Education Press Limited Company. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42524-022-0243-z>

Liu, H. J., Love, P. E., Smith, J., Irani, Z., Hajli, N., & Sing, M. C. (2018). From design to operations: a process management life-cycle performance measurement system for Public-Private Partnerships. *Production Planning & Control*, 29(1), 68-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2017.1382740>

Lozano, R., Lukman, R., Lozano, F. J., Huisingh, D., & Lambrechts, W. (2013). Declarations for sustainability in higher education: becoming better leaders, through addressing the university system. *Journal of cleaner production*, 48, 10-19.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.006>

Lu, L., Lu, A. C. C., Gursoy, D., & Neale, N. R. (2016). Work engagement, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions: A comparison between supervisors and line-level employees. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(4), 737-761. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-07-2014-0360>

Magutu, P. O. (2016). Quality Management Systems and Quality Improvement in Kenyan Universities. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(7), 1004-1020. . <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-08-2015-0118>

Martins, L. C., Santos, L., & Ramos, C. M. Q. (2019). Quality Management in Higher Education: An Exploratory Study. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(3), 241-260. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-09-2018-0091>

McKay, J., O'Neill, D., & Petrakieva, L. (2018). CAKES (Cultural awareness and knowledge exchange scheme): a holistic and inclusive approach to supporting international students. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 42(2), 276-288. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2016.1261092>

Miranda, R. D., & Reyes-Chua, E. (2021). Best practices in quality assurance in selected higher education institutions (Heis) in the Philippines in the light of the Malcolm baldrige framework. *WSEAS Transactions on Environment and Development*, 17, 533-545. <https://doi.org/10.37394/232015.2021.17.51>

Mohammad, M., Yaakub, N. H., Yahya, M. S., & Hamid, N. A. A. (2016). Awareness, implementation, effectiveness and future adoption of operational improvement initiatives: Survey results. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management* (Vol. 8-10 March 2016, p. 654). IEOM Society. <https://bit.ly/3XrwZlc>

Montano, D. E., Montano, E., & Waissbluth, R. (2019). Quality Management Systems in Higher Education: A Study of Accreditation Processes in Latin America. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(3), 280-296. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-11-2018-0095>

Mourad, M. (2017). Quality assurance as a driver of information management strategy: Stakeholders' perspectives in higher education. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 30(5), 779-794. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-06-2016-0104>

Myna, Z., Yarka, U., Peleschyshyn, O., & Bilushchak, T. (2016, February). Using international standards of quality management system in higher educational institutions. In *2016 13th International Conference on Modern Problems of Radio Engineering, Telecommunications and Computer Science (TCSET)* (pp. 834-837). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSET.2016.7452199>

Naanep, N. D., & Cerado, E. C. (2023). Quality Management System and Institutional Performance among State Universities and Colleges (Sucs) In Region XII, Philippines. *SDSSU Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(1), 22-28. <https://smrj.nemsu.edu.ph/index.php/SMRJ/article/view/231>

Negron, L. A. (2020). Relationship between quality management practices, performance and maturity quality management, a contingency approach. *Quality Management Journal*, 27(4), 215-228. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10686967.2020.1809582>

Neyestani, B. and Juanzon, J.B.. (2017) ISO 9001 Standard and Organization's Performance: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(2), 6-13. <https://doi.org/10.22192/ijamr.2017.04.02.002>

NIST (2004). *Education Criteria for Performance Excellence*, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD.

Oakland, J. S. (2014). *Total Quality Management and Operational Excellence: Text with Cases*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315815725>

Ocan, A. (2019). Impact of ISO 9001 Quality Management System on Organizational Performance: A Case of a Private University in Uganda. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 27(4), 419-436. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-11-2018-0071>

Paliulis, N. K., & Labanauskis, R. (2015). Benchmarking as an instrument for improvement of quality management in higher education. *Business, management and education*, 13(1), 140-157. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=285897>

Panigrahi, S. S., Bahinipati, B., & Jain, V. (2019, July 9). Sustainable supply chain management: A review of literature and implications for future research. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*. Emerald Group Holdings Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-01-2018-0003>

Papanthymou, A., & Darra, M. (2017). Quality Management in Higher Education: Review and Perspectives. *Higher Education Studies*, 7(3), 132. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v7n3p132>

Pappas, I. O., Mikalef, P., Giannakos, M. N., Krogstie, J., & Lekakos, G. (2018). Big data and business analytics ecosystems: paving the way towards digital transformation and sustainable societies. *Information systems and e-business management*, 16(3), 479-491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-021-00538-z>

Polatcan, M., Arslan, P., & Balci, A. (2023). The mediating effect of teacher self-efficacy regarding the relationship between transformational school leadership and teacher agency. *Educational Studies*, 49(5), 823-841.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2021.1894549>

Pratoom, K. (2018). Differential relationship of person-and task-focused leadership to team effectiveness: A meta-analysis of moderators. *Human Resource Development Review*, 17(4), 393-439. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484318790167>.

Rahman, M. N. A., & Sambasivan, M. (2016). The Impact of ISO 9001 Certification on Academic Performance: A Case Study of a Malaysian University. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 27(5-6), 633-649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2014.1003952>

Rawashdeh, A. M., Almasarweh, M. S., Alhyasat-Al-Balqa, E. B., & Rawashdeh, O. M. (2021). The Relationship Between the Quality Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance Via the Mediating Role of Organizational Learning. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 15(2), 373-386. <https://doi.org/10.24874/IJQR15.02-01>

Razak, R. A., Yusoff, R. M., & Hashim, N. I. H. (2016). Quality Management in Higher Education: Review and Future Directions. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 24(3), 249-270. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-02-2016-0009>

Republic Act No. 7722, An act creating the commission on higher education, appropriating funds therefor and for other purposes. <https://bit.ly/3VjmSMs>

Rizos, S., Sfakianaki, E., & Kakouris, A. (2022). Quality of Administrative Services in Higher Education. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 5(2), 115-128 <https://doi.org/10.12973/eujem.5.2.115>

Rodrigues, M., & Franco, M. (2019). The corporate sustainability strategy in organisations: A systematic review and future directions. *Sustainability*, 11(22), 6214. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11226214>

Rubel, A., & Jones, K. (2017). Data Analytics in Higher Education: Key Concerns and Open Questions. *University of St. Thomas Journal of Law and Public Policy*, 11(1), 25. <http://ir.stthomas.edu/ustjlpp>

Ryan, T. (2015). Quality assurance in higher education: A review of literature. *Higher learning research communications*, 5(4), n4. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18870/hlrc.v5i4.257>

Sattler, C., & Sonntag, K. (2018). Quality cultures in higher education institutions—development of the Quality Culture Inventory. *Geographies of the University*, 313-327. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75593-9_9

Scott, L. (2016). Baldrige {Criteria} {Commentary} ({Health} {Care}). NIST. <https://www.nist.gov/baldrige/baldrige-criteria-commentary-health-care>

Seale, J., Gibson, S., Haynes, J., & Potter, A. (2015). Power and Resistance: Reflections on the Rhetoric and Reality of Using Participatory Methods to Promote Student Voice and Engagement in Higher Education. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 39(4), 534-552. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2014.938264>

Sfreddo, L. S., Vieira, G. B. B., Vidor, G., & Santos, C. H. S. (2021). ISO 9001 based quality management systems and organisational performance: a systematic literature review. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2018.1549939>

Shehabat, I. M., & Berrish, M. (2021). Integration between knowledge management and total quality management in Jordanian Universities: Empirical study. In *Research Anthology on Preparing School Administrators to Lead Quality Education Programs* (pp. 1405-1436). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2016.1238760>

Shevchenko, I., Semenova, A., ... Sharonova, N. (2021). Development of a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of higher education institutions departments. *Engineering and Educational Technologies*, 9(3), 42-53. <https://doi.org/10.30929/2307-9770.2021.09.03.04>

Shrouf, H., Al-Qudah, S., Khawaldeh, K., Obeidat, A., & Rawashdeh, A. J. M. S. L. (2020). A study on relationship between human resources and strategic performance: The mediating role of productivity. *Management Science Letters*, 10(13), 3189-3196. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.5.002>

Silva, D. S., de Moraes, G. S. M., Makiya, I. K., & Giocondo, F. I. (2016). Quality Assurance in Education Measurement of perceived service quality in higher education institutions: a review of HEDPERF scale use. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 25(4). <https://bit.ly/3z8cqAk>

Smith, C., & Brown, D. (2018). The impact of strategic communication on institutional effectiveness in higher education. *Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(2), 120-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2023.101524>

Solomon, M. A., Studies, B., Lecturer, S., & Studies, P. (2023). Continuous Professional Development in Higher Education : A Systematic Review of its Conceptualizations , Trends and Challenges (2011- 2020). *Bahir Dar Journal of Education*, 23(1), 21-39. <https://doi.org/10.4314/bdje.v23i1>.

- Speklé, R. F., & Verbeeten, F. H. (2014). The use of performance measurement systems in the public sector: Effects on performance. *Management Accounting Research*, 25(2), 131–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mar.2013.07.004>
- Steigenberger, N., & Ebers, M. (2023). What drives integration teams to achieve high integration process performance in absorption acquisitions? A configurational analysis. *Long range planning*, 56(6), 102330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2023.102330>
- Sukkar, M. Y. (2022). Quality management in higher education institutions (HEI). *Khartoum Medical Journal*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.53332/kmj.v10i3.660>
- Tambare, P., Meshram, C., Lee, C. C., Ramteke, R. J., & Imoize, A. L. (2021). Performance measurement system and quality management in data-driven Industry 4.0: A review. *Sensors*, 22(1), 224. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22010224>
- Taroreh, S. R. A., Saerang, D. P. E., Maramis, J., Worang, F. G., & Wenas, R. S. (2022). Implementation of Total Quality Management In Higher Education Institutions: A Literature Review. *Jurnal EMBA : Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v10i2.41365>
- Tasopoulou, K., & Tsiotras, G. (2017). Benchmarking towards excellence in higher education. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 24(3), 617-634. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-03-2016-0036>
- Tausif, M. R. (2017). Assessing the quality of education in Saudi Arabia. *International journal of economic research*, 14(17), 521-528. <https://bit.ly/3z3iMke>
- Texeira-Quiros, J., Justino, M. do R., Antunes, M. G., Mucharreira, P. R., & Nunes, A. de T. (2022). Effects of Innovation, Total Quality Management, and Internationalization on Organizational Performance of Higher Education Institutions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.869638>
- Tworek, K., Bieńkowska, A., & Zabłocka-Kluczka, A. (2020). Organizational reliability: Human resources, information technology and management. *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003047995>
- Virtanen, A., & Tynjälä, P. (2018). Factors explaining the learning of generic skills: a study of university students' experiences. *Teaching in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2018.1515195>
- Vykydal, D., Folta, M., & Nenadál, J. (2020). A study of quality assessment in higher education within the context of sustainable development: A case study from Czech Republic. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114769>
- Wassan, A. N., Memon, M. S., Mari, S. I., & Kalwar, M. A. (2022). Impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices on Sustainability and Organisational Performance. *Journal of Applied Research in Technology & Engineering*, 3(2), 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.4995/jarte.2022.17408>
- Weldeslassie, S. (2021). Basis for policy formulation: Systematic policy analysis or intuitive policy decision?. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 13(1), 11-19. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JPAPR2015.0348>
- Yu, G. J., Park, M., & Hong, K. H. (2020). A strategy perspective on total quality management. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 31(1–2), 68–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2017.1412256>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jonathan P. Roque

Sultan Kudarat State University – Philippines